

Expressing averaging as a recursive linear mix formula

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Abstract.

Usually averaging is done by summing terms and dividing this resulting total by a term count. However, averaging procedure can be done strictly recursively and in a linear way. In this paper I'll show how to do that and I will derive target formula from a standard averaging expression. Recursive averaging procedure may be useful in embedded systems, etc.

Usual notation for an averaging procedure is this :

$$\bar{x}_n = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_{n-1} + x_n}{n} \quad (1)$$

Separating last term and multiplying first term's numerator and denominator by $(n - 1)$ gives :

$$\bar{x}_n = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_{n-1}}{n-1} \times \frac{n-1}{n} + \frac{x_n}{n} \quad (2)$$

Noticing that product first term is nothing more, but a previous recursive function value, let's us to simplify expression :

$$\bar{x}_n = \frac{n-1}{n} \cdot \bar{x}_{n-1} + \frac{x_n}{n} \quad (3)$$

Multiplying first product term's numerator and denominator by $1/n$, we arrive at final recursive averaging linear mix formula :

$$\bar{x}_n = (1 - \alpha) \bar{x}_{n-1} + \alpha x_n \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha = 1/n$.

As a side-note, it is seen from a recursive formula when $n \rightarrow \infty, \alpha \rightarrow 0$ and (4) expression's right side limit becomes :

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} (1 - \alpha) \bar{x}_{n-1} + \alpha x_n = \bar{x}_{n-1} \quad (5)$$

Thus for a very big iteration number n simply $\bar{x}_n \approx \bar{x}_{n-1}$. So to say average value converges into some constant and this means that it is impractical to average huge arrays of numbers. In most cases it is enough to average a randomly sampled smaller set of numbers if smaller accuracy is not a critical issue.

Conclusions. Starting from a standard way to express an averaging procedure, recursive averaging linear mix formula (4) was derived. It may be useful in resource-constrained systems as well as for saving computer memory space (no need to store a total variable). Also (4) formula may be useful for predicting/modeling average value fluctuations. Also using (5) limit expression, an averaging recurrence series convergence fact was determined, which shows that it is not necessary to average all numbers in a set to get an approximate average value.